

Sample Size Calculation for Time-to-Event Endpoints with Extreme Hazard Ratios

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Abstract

The Schoenfeld formula is widely used to estimate the number of events required for event-driven trials. However, it is derived from the score test and may exhibit bias when the hazard ratio deviates significantly from the null value of 1. To address this issue, we present a straightforward simulation approach that demonstrates robust performance across various scenarios.

Key Words: Hazard ratio, sample size calculation, Schoenfeld formula

1. Introduction

The Schoenfeld formula (Schoenfeld, 1983) is commonly used to calculate the necessary number of events for powering clinical trials with time-to-event endpoints under the proportional hazards assumption. Specifically, let α denote the one-sided significance level, γ the type II error, β_0 the log hazard ratio under the null hypothesis, and β_1 the log hazard ratio under the alternative hypothesis. Additionally, let ζ denote the randomization ratio between treatment and control groups. The Schoenfeld formula estimates the required number of events D as follows

$$D = \frac{(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma})^2 (1 + \zeta)^2}{(\beta_1 - \beta_0)^2 \zeta} \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, the number of patients to randomize and the study duration can be determined by assuming an enrollment model, event model, and dropout model. This framework has served as the foundation for conventional sample size calculations for survival analysis in most statistical software packages.

However, the Schoenfeld formula is based on the score test under the null hypothesis $H_0: \beta = 0$. If the true hazard ratio, $\exp(\beta)$, deviates significantly from the null value of 1, this formula can lead to substantial bias in the estimated number of events required.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 will provide a motivating example that illustrates the bias of the Schoenfeld formula with extreme hazard ratios. Section 3 will describe our proposed method to yield an unbiased estimation of the required number of events even with extreme hazard ratios. In Section 4, we perform extensive simulations to demonstrate the validity of the proposed method across a wide range of simulation scenarios. We conclude the article with the software implementation of the proposed method.

2. Motivating Example

To illustrate the impact of extreme hazard ratios on power estimates, consider the following scenario:

- Target power: 90%
- One-sided significance level: 0.025

- Constant enrollment rate: 20 patients per month
- Randomization ratios: 1:1 or 3:1
- Dropout probability: 10% over 2 years for both groups
- Event rate: 1.9 patients per year in the control group
- Hazard ratio: 0.3 (indicating an extreme hazard ratio context)

For the 1:1 randomization case, applying the Schoenfeld formula (1) yields

$$D = \frac{(\Phi^{-1}(1 - 0.025) + \Phi^{-1}(1 - 0.1))^2}{(\log(0.3))^2} \times 4 = 29$$

Next, we examine the relationship between the number of subjects and study duration. As illustrated in Figure 1, there is a significant decrease in study duration as we initially increase the number of subjects; however, this effect plateaus after exceeding 75 subjects.

Figure 1: Relationship between study duration and the number of subjects for a hazard ratio of 0.3 under a 1:1 randomization.

Assuming 76 subjects, we conduct a simulation study to estimate the empirical power, which results in 87.6%. Since this empirical power falls short of the target power of 90%, it suggests that the Schoenfeld formula yields an overly optimistic estimate of required events in this case.

For the 3:1 randomization scenario, the Schoenfeld formula indicates the need for 39 events. Randomizing 104 patients yields an empirical power of 95.3%, indicating an overly conservative estimate of events required.

3. Proposed Method

We assume that the required number of events, D , is proportional to $(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma})^2$. The proportionality constant K is independent of the Type I and Type II errors, leading to

$$D = K(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma})^2 \quad (2)$$

Let D_s represent the number of events calculated via the Schoenfeld formula, and $1 - \gamma_s$ denote the corresponding empirical power. By (2), we have

$$D_s = K(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma_s})^2 \quad (3)$$

Using (2) and (3), we can derive

$$D = D_s \frac{(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma})^2}{(z_{1-\alpha} + z_{1-\gamma_s})^2} \quad (4)$$

Thus, our approach utilizes simulations to calibrate the actual required number of events.

Revisiting the motivating example for the 1:1 randomization case, we find from (4) that

$$D = 29 \times \left(\frac{\Phi^{-1}(1 - 0.025) + \Phi^{-1}(1 - 0.1)}{\Phi^{-1}(1 - 0.025) + \Phi^{-1}(0.876)} \right)^2 = 31.4$$

This rounds up to 32 events. A simulation shows an empirical power of 90.5%, aligning with the target. Similarly, for the 3:1 case, the required events adjust to 31, yielding an empirical power of 90.8%. Table 1 summarizes the findings obtained from the Schoenfeld formula and the proposed method.

Table 1: Comparison of empirical power for the motivating example between the Schoenfeld formula and the proposed method

<i>Randomization Ratio</i>	<i>Schoenfeld formula</i>		<i>Proposed method</i>	
	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Empirical Power</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Empirical Power</i>
1:1	29	87.6%	32	90.5%
3:1	39	95.3%	31	90.8%

4. Simulation Study

We assess the proposed approach under various simulation scenarios, including variable follow-up schemes typical in oncology studies and fixed follow-up schemes more common in non-oncology studies. Our scenarios include:

- Target power: 90% for phase 3 studies and 80% for phase 2 studies
- Balanced randomization, along with two unbalanced ratios (2:1 and 3:1)
- Hazard ratios ranging from 0.20 to 0.80 in increments of 0.05

For fixed designs, we set the follow-up duration at 6.5 months, adjusting the number of subjects accordingly.

Figure 2 illustrates the simulation results comparing the proposed method with the Schoenfeld formula under a variable follow-up design. The Schoenfeld formula tends to underestimate the required number of events for the 1:1 randomization ratio, while it overestimates the required events for the 2:1 and 3:1 randomization ratios, particularly when extreme hazard ratios are present. Notably, the overestimation is more pronounced for the 3:1 randomization compared to the 2:1 ratio. In contrast, the proposed method reliably provides the necessary event counts to achieve the target power across various scenarios.

Figure 2: Comparison of empirical power between the Schoenfeld formula and the proposed method under a variable follow-up design. The top row represents a target power of 90%, while the bottom row corresponds to a target power of 80%. From left to right, the three columns illustrate the results for randomization ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1, respectively.

Figure 3 presents the simulation results comparing the proposed method with the Schoenfeld formula under a fixed follow-up design. The findings are consistent with those observed in the variable follow-up design.

Figure 3: Comparison of empirical power between the Schoenfeld formula and the proposed method under a fixed follow-up design. The top row represents a target power of 90%, while the bottom row corresponds to a target power of 80%. From left to right, the three columns illustrate the results for randomization ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1, respectively.

5. Software Implementation

The `lrschoenfeld` function in the `lrstat` R package (Lu, 2025) can be used to obtain required event numbers and study designs based on both the Schoenfeld formula and our proposed method.

To utilize the Schoenfeld method, set `calibrate = 0`. To apply the proposed method, set `calibrate = 1`.

For the motivating example involving a 3:1 randomization ratio, the following function call can be used to obtain the results for the Schoenfeld method, which yields an empirical power of 95.3%.

```
lr1 <- lrschoenfeld(  
  beta = 0.1, alpha = 0.025,  
  allocationRatioPlanned = 3,  
  accrualIntensity = 20, hazardRatio = 0.3,  
  lambda2 = 1.9/12,  
  gamma1 = -log(1-0.1)/24, gamma2 = -log(1-0.1)/24,  
  calibrate = 0, maxNumberOfIterations = 10000,  
  seed = 12345)
```

lr1\$simulationResults

By executing the following function call, we can obtain the results for the proposed method, which yields an empirical power of 90.8%.

```
lr2 <- lrschoenfeld(  
  beta = 0.1, alpha = 0.025,  
  allocationRatioPlanned = 3,  
  accrualIntensity = 20, hazardRatio = 0.3,  
  lambda2 = 1.9/12,  
  gamma1 = -log(1-0.1)/24, gamma2 = -log(1-0.1)/24,  
  calibrate = 1, maxNumberOfIterations = 10000,  
  seed = 12345)
```

lr2\$simulationResults

In summary, the bias in the Schoenfeld formula increases with more extreme hazard ratios and unbalanced randomization ratios. In contrast, the proposed method remains effective regardless of study designs, randomization ratios, target powers, and hazard ratios.

References

- Schoenfeld, D. A. (1983). Sample-size formula for the proportional-hazards regression model. *Biometrics*, 499-503.
- Lu, K. (2025). *lrstat: Power and Sample Size Calculation for Non-Proportional Hazards and Beyond*. R package version 0.2.15, <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/lrstat/index.html>